
**PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND THE NEXUS OF IPPIS
IN NIGERIAN FEDERAL UNIVERSITIES: A CASE ANALYSIS OF
UNIVERSITY OF UYO**

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Abstract

The fact of its topical and sensitive objectives which are to ensure that public funds are frugally managed according to laid down principles is rather paradoxical as far as public financial management and integrated payroll and personnel information system are concerned. Due to the paradox, this study was set to unravel the nexus between the two variables and thereby proffer solutions to the systemic payroll dis-functions occurring in the public financial system in the Nigerian Federal Universities. The study aimed at achieving three subsidiary objectives, among others was to establish whether the intention of government was right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria. In order to achieve this, the study asked three research questions and postulated three null hypotheses to empirically test the responses of respondents and arrive at findings. Over 175 academic and non-academic staff of University of Uyo were observed, interviewed or served with structured questionnaire, respectively. The study adopted a qualitative research paradigm, which helped the researcher to carry out the combination of explanatory, descriptive and contextual approaches in arriving at the conclusion of the research. Frustration-Aggression theory. At the end of the research, three findings were made, among others included: that government intention was actually right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria, but the pains associated with it far outweigh the gains of IPPIS, as an attempt to frustrate staff welfare which is tantamount to bad governance. Based on the findings, three recommendations were proffered that the Federal Government should listen to the complains of ASUU and endeavour to reduce to the barest minimum, the pains associated with IPPIS, or otherwise should replace IPPIS with UTAS.

Keywords: Public Financial Management, Nexus, IPPIS, Federal Universities, University of Uyo, UTAS.

1. Introduction

In the early stage, the concept of ‘public financial management’ is pivotal or paramount in all spheres of economic endeavours in our contemporary society today, be it in the developed, developing or even in the underdeveloped worlds. Like Ime T. Akpan has stated in his foreword in Nwaeze (2009), “its topical and sensitive objectives are to ensure that public funds are frugally managed according to laid down principles”. Folorunso, *et al* (2021) are worried that, ‘in Nigeria, the issue of public service salary has been at the forefront right from early stage of Nigerian nationhood. While the mode of payment evolved from time to time, the minimum wage was a subject of unending debates between labour and government in Nigeria.

In earlier the stage, payments were done through cash payment, cheque, bank overdraft and later bank transfer after the bank’s reconsolidation. Unlike America and Europe, period of salary payment in Nigeria is usually a month and this is a popular practice in the public service. Being a federal state, the issue of minimum wages and method of payment implementation had generated a lot of crises between states and the federal government. Most times, the states refused to pay the new implemented minimum wage on the excuse of not being economically buoyant to do so thus leaving state employees pauperized.

Interestingly, every administration, be it public or private is faced with the issues of financial management in government, institutions or corporate organizations. In the light of this, every administrator is duty-bound to manage the scarce resources at his disposal in such a manner as it is equitable and in accordance with the laid down principles. But, in this study our focus will be particularly on the public sector financial management which comprises basically the governments, civil service and public institutions or agencies. Public financial management is an important aspect of governance and public affairs. It has to do with the proper financial book-keeping or the administration of the spending of government funds. Without finance, government cannot function. The functioning of government is in the public sphere, therefore, its finance is public finance. It should be noted that public finance requires proper management. Public finance requires judicious spending in order to guide against fraud, misappropriation, corruption and financial improprieties.

On the other hand, the financial system of IPPIS which is the acronym of Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System was conceptualized in October, 2006 by the Federal Government. This was to serve as one of its

reform programmes to improve the effectiveness and efficiency in the storage of personnel records and administration of monthly payroll in such a way to enhance confidence in staff members of Nigerian Federal Universities.

“Since the return of civil rule 1999, lots of reforms have been carried out in the Nigerian public service which has revolutionized salary administration. The recent salary administration reform came with the introduction of electronic payment system which was designed to replace the cumbersome obsolete process that has characterized salary payment. It was on this basis that the federal government introduced the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) to efficiently and effectively meet the needs of public servants in Nigeria and to block leakages and corruption in public service through payroll system, although, the introduction and implementation of IPPIS were faced with slight resistance from few segments of the federal government Ministry, Department and Agency” (Folorunso and Simeon, 2021).

The concept of Public Financial Management is pivotal or paramount in all spheres of economic endeavours in our contemporary society today, be it in the developed, developing or even in the underdeveloped worlds. In an attempt to unbundle the subject of public financial management, one would have to concentrate on the economic processes and activities of sourcing for funds, utilizing and managing them effectively and efficiently in order to achieve the desired economic goals and objectives as:

- (i) Resource allocation in the economy.
- (ii) Economic stabilization through price stability, exchange rate stability, interest rate stability,
- (iii) Promotion of equity in income and wealth distribution in the economy.
- (iv) Stimulation of growth and development in the economy to ensure high level employment, per capita income and standard of living.

In Nigeria, Public Financial Management has gone through series of phases. Such financial practices as Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS), University Transparency and Accountability Solution (UTAS) as an alternative to IPPIS, International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAs), e-banking, e-payment and Treasury Single Account (TSA) of the President Muhammadu Buhari’s administration, etc. which should be able to curb the excesses of public financial management seem not to be very effective in the Nigeria financial sector.

As Folorunso, *et al.* (2021) have held that, ‘‘Since the return of civil rule 1999, lots of reforms have been carried out in the Nigerian public service which has revolutionized salary administration. The recent salary administration reform came with the introduction of electronic payment system which was designed to replace the cumbersome obsolete process that has characterized salary payment. It was on this basis that the federal government introduced the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) to efficiently and effectively meet the needs of public servants in Nigeria and to block leakages and corruption in public service through payroll system, although, the introduction and implementation of IPPIS were faced with slight resistance from few segments of the federal government Ministry, Department and Agency’’.

The major benefits of IPPIS to participants which are supposed to include: accurate and reliable personnel information, reduction or elimination of corrupt and sharp practices, facilitation of modern scientific and accurate budgeting and forecasting have rather than provide the aforementioned major benefits to staff of Nigerian Federal Universities, but seems to have become more problematic than problem-solving. IPPIS seems to have suddenly become more patient than the physician that it was conceptualized to be.

It is quite unfortunate that the level of expected results is not at any time commensurate with the efforts of government in the aspect of devising the most appropriate public financial management method to solve its age-long public financial problems. Rather, the various government methods, as mentioned above have suffered the problem of implementation, mismanagement, corruption, or outright rejection like IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). So far, it is on record that ‘‘there are 696 MDAs on IPPIS Platform as at June, 2020. The department is responsible for processing and payment of salary to over one million (1,139,633) Federal Government Employees across the 696 MDAs. Yet, the salaries of 243 workers have been suspended for failure to update their records online on the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS).

Also, in attempting to find the nexus of IPPIS with Public Financial Management it will raise a need to ex-ray the cardinal objectives of IPPIS, which according to the Office of Accountant General of the Federation, (2020) in Folorunso, *et al.* (2021) include, but not limited to the following:

- i. To facilitate human resource planning and by providing information for decision making;

- ii. To provide a platform for accurate budgeting of annual recurrent expenditure on staff emoluments;
- iii. To monitor monthly payment of staff emoluments against FGN's annual Budget to ensure minimal wastage and leakage;
- iv. To facilitate easy storage, updating and retrieval of personnel record for administrative and pension processing;
- v. To ensure database integrity such that, data once entered cannot be manipulated by unauthorized users;
- vi. To eliminate payroll fraud such as multiple payment of emoluments to a single employee or payment of monthly salary to a non-existent employee;
- vii. To ascertain actual personnel emoluments of the Federal Government employee; etc.

The various complains by participants of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) despite the clear objectives of the policy as stated above, particularly in the University of Uyo, have become the major reasons why this study is carried out. The study will show a connect between public financial management and Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) as regards the payment of monthly salaries of ASUU members in the Nigerian Federal Universities, particularly in Uniuyo.

The Objectives of this study will be in two-folds: the main and the subsidiary objectives.

The main objective of the study will be to unravel the nexus of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) as it relates to public financial management in Nigeria, with particular focus on the University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The subsidiary objectives will be subdivided into three, as follows:

- i. To establish whether the intention of government was right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria;
- ii. To ascertain if the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has served the purpose in 696 MDAs who are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria;
- iii. To find out the reasons for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU).

In order to elicit useful answers to aid the achievement of this study the three questions below were asked:

- i. Was the intention of government right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria?
- ii. How can the study ascertain if the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has served the purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria?
- iii. What are the reasons for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU)?

For the purpose of making objective and accurate findings on the above topic, three (3) Null Hypotheses (Ho:) were postulated as follows:

- i. The intention of government did not seem right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria.
- ii. The study may not ascertain if the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has served the purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria.
- iii. There is no cogent reason for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU).

The significance of the research on this all-important topic that bothers on public financial management and the nexus of IPPIS is enormous. The research will provide a useful guide to the public on why government came up with the policy, at the first instance, and what its intention was at the inception of the policy. With that, policy makers and implementers will know how to carry out their assigned duties to the betterment of the beneficiaries of the policy. On the other hand, the beneficiaries of the policy will also know their roles and the appropriate time to carry out their assigned roles.

Finally, the researchers, students and indeed, the general public will come to terms with the reasons why IPPIS could be working for up to 696 MDAs and not working for ASUU.

Operationalization of Concepts:

- i. **Public Financial Management:** Public financial management is an important aspect of governance and public affairs. It has to do with the proper financial book-keeping or the administration of the spending of government funds.
- ii. **Nexus:** The word, ‘nexus’ means a connection or series of connections linking two or more things, e.g. ‘the nexus between industry and political power; or, in our own sense, ‘the nexus between public financial management and IPPIS.

- iii. **IPPIS:** This is the acronym of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System. It is one of the reform programmes to improve the effectiveness and efficiency in the storage of personnel records and administration of monthly payroll in such a way to enhance confidence in staff members of Nigerian Federal Universities.
- iv. **Federal Universities:** Federal Universities are those universities established and owned by the Federal Government of Nigeria. Some Federal Universities might also have been taken over from the original owners by the Federal Government, as the case may be. However, below are the names of the Federal Universities in Nigeria and their years of establishment.
- v. **University of Uyo:** The University of Uyo is located in Uyo, capital of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The university was formally known as the University of Cross River State. On October, 1991 the Federal Government of Nigeria established it as a Federal University and the name was changed to the University of Uyo and abbreviated, Uniuyo.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Public Financial Management (PFM):

“Public Financial Management”, according to Nwaeze (2009), can be defined as “an aspect of finance which studies the effective and efficient sourcing and utilization of the financial resources of the public sector for the attainment of set objectives and goals”. The subject is highly related to public finance. While public finance deals with the various sources and uses of funds in the government or public sector, including the problems that results from the power of government to tax and statutory limitations on how political units may raise funds and what the funds may be used for; the objectives of public financial management is to fulfill certain basic financial obligations within the sector, which are necessary for the achievement of higher level income and employment; to promote some particular aspects of economic justice by income redistribution through taxes and other pending activities of government; and to ensure realistic provision and distribution of certain demanded social goods and services to the public.

The subject matter of public financial management today concentrates on the economic processes and activities of sourcing funds, utilizing and managing them effectively and efficiently in order to achieve the desired economic goals and objectives as:

- i) Resource allocation in the economy.
- ii) Economic stabilization through price stability, exchange rate stability, interest rate stability,
- iii) Promotion of equity in income and wealth distribution in the economy.
- iv) Stimulation of growth and development in the economy to ensure high level employment, per capita income and standard of living.

All these are aimed at meeting the welfare needs of the citizenry through adequate provision of social goods. The economic processes and activities involved in public financial management centre around:

- a) **Financial Planning:** This involves preparing a course of action, setting out desired objectives, determining strategy and alternative courses of action to achieve set objectives.
- b) **Financial Decision:** This involves identification and selection of the appropriate (best) course of action that would help maximize objectives.
- c) **Financial Control:** This involves establishing standards on which actual performance could be compared and corrective action taken on deviations or variances noticed.

2.2 Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS):

The Integrated Personnel Payroll System is a public payroll system developed by the World Bank and adopted by the federal government in 2007 to improve the transparency and accountability in the management of personnel payroll. The Integrated Personnel Payroll System operates under the office of the Accountant General of the Federation and is charged with the payment of salaries, removal of deductibles, and management of government's payroll.

The IPPIS has about 600 MDAs that have enrolled as of June 2020. The IPPIS department is charged with the processing of salaries of federal government workers in all MDAs that have been captured. The IPPIS has also been engaged in controversies recently especially with the Academic Staff Union of Universities who have blamed the platform for shortchanging them and removing deductibles that they did not subscribe to. The federal government of Nigeria in October 2006 introduced the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) as one of its reform programmes to improve the effectiveness and efficiency in the storage of personnel records and administration of monthly payroll in such a way to enhance confidence in staff emolument costs and budgeting.

According to top government staff, the aim was to buttress the government's commitment to efficient and effective service delivery. "Our main aim is to pay accurately and on time within statutory and contractual regulations. We aim to provide a payroll service that is customer-focused and that utilizes technology wherever possible." As at June 2020, there were 696 ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) on the IPPIS platform. The department is responsible for processing and payment of salaries to over one million (1,139,633) federal government employees across the 696 MDAs. Our main aim is to pay accurately and on time within statutory and contractual regulations. We aim to provide a payroll service that is customer-focused and that utilizes technology wherever possible." The goal of IPPIS as a payment system is to enroll into the platform, all the federal government MDAs that draws personnel cost fund from the consolidated funds of the Federal Government of Nigeria.

The goal of IPPIS as a payment system is to enroll into the platform, all the federal government MDAs that draws personnel cost fund from the consolidated revenue fund. Since the inception of the IPPIS project in April 2007, the department has saved the federal government billions of Naira by eliminating thousands of ghost workers.

- i. violate the 2009 Agreement which was negotiated, agreed and signed by ASUU and FGN;
- ii. The IPPIS template is designed to phase out staff who are above (60) years, which contradicts the new policy of Professors retiring at (70) years;
- iii. IPPIS does not recognize payment of promotion arrears, rent allowances as it is now consolidated in our (academic staff) salary;
- iv. IPPIS does not capture the technicalities and peculiarities associated with the flexibility and mobility of academics in the university system;
- v. The IPPIS template adopts a tax payment system known as ptax2 which is inimical to our members on consolidated salary.

The federal government of Nigeria in October 2006 introduced the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) as one of its reform programmes to improve the effectiveness and efficiency in the storage of personnel records and administration of monthly payroll in such a way to enhance confidence in staff emolument costs and budgeting. According to top government staff, the aim was to buttress the government's commitment to efficient and effective service delivery. "Our main aim is to pay accurately and on time within statutory and contractual regulations. But, on the contrary, Lecturers working for Federal Universities currently face herculean tasks of

embarking on sabbaticals as a result of the launch of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS). The reason being that it does not offer the solution that it was meant to give, rather it has succeeded to bring thousands of University staff into poverty and untold hardship (Udoh, 2006).

The choice of IPPIS as a payment system is copied from what is obtainable in other parts of the world where Information Communication Technology (ICT) is used to improve management reporting. It was established to help the government track ghost workers in its payment system. The World Bank-financed the pilot phase in February 2006 upon the approval of the Federal Executive Council (FEC) for the Bureau of Public Service Reforms (BPSR). However, the project went live in April 2007 with seven pilot MDAs, with their management transferred to the Office of the Accountant General of the Federation (OAGF) in October 2008. The pilot MDAs are the federal ministry of education; federal ministry of transportation (works arm); federal ministry of finance; budget office of the federation; federal ministry of information; ministry of foreign affairs; and national planning commission. Prior to their registration, the nominal rolls of the seven pilot MDAs submitted indicated 55,000 staff, hence World Bank paid for 55,000 licenses. However, after their enrolment into the scheme, it was discovered that their total staff strength was 32,000, resulting to 11 MDAs being brought on board in July 2009 to optimize the 55,000 licenses purchased.

The federal executive council has seen the benefits of the scheme, especially in the area of savings to the government in its meeting on Wednesday 1 December 2010 approved the enrolment of all MDAs that draw their personnel cost from the consolidated revenue fund (CRF) into the IPPIS. The phase II service-wide implementation commenced under the platform of new software called Oracle Application in September 2011 in batches and is being financed by the federal government of Nigeria. As of April 2018, 490 MDAs, including the Nigeria Police and other paramilitary agencies have been enrolled into IPPIS with total staff strength of over 700,000 employees.

2.3 Reasons for ASUU and other MDAs' Resistance of IPPIS

According to Folorunso, *et al.* (2021), Academic Staff Union of University and other MDAs have shown displeasure over the plan to migrate them on IPPIS. According to the ASUU, enforcing IPPIS is an infringement on universities' right to autonomy. During a discussion with the Senate on the rejection, ASUU President, Professor Biodun Ogunyemi in ASUU Bulletin September, 2019 mentioned that the enforcement is not permitted under the law. "The

introduction of IPPIS is not backed by law. The Union's position is that there are extant legal provisions and negotiated agreements arising from the nature and peculiarities of Nigerian universities, which make IPPIS unnecessary and inapplicable to the universities".

As an entity, a Nigerian university is backed by an Act giving it the freedom to run itself and the introduction of a central payroll system is an infringement on this right. The IPPIS software is not robust enough to cater for the peculiarities of lecturers (ASUU Bulletin September, 2019). Outside universities, the Petroleum and Natural Gas Senior Staff Association of Nigeria (PENGASSAN) embarked on an industrial action earlier in November, 2020 over disagreements with the federal government on IPPIS.

In the series of resolutions ASUU published to its members and the press in November 2019, (ASUU, 27th November 2019 Resolutions in Folorunso, *et al.* (2021)) ASUU highlighted reasons why its Union refused to enroll on IPPIS to include:

- i. IPPIS violates university autonomy as enshrined in section 2AA of the University (Miscellaneous) provisions Amendment Act 2003 which states that the powers of Council shall be exercised as in the law and statutes of each University and to that extent establishment circulars that are inconsistent with the laws and statutes of the university shall not apply to the universities;
- ii. The peculiar nature of the appointment of the university academics.

Apart from ASUU, NNPC subsidiaries too opposed the plan to enroll on IPPIS. The affected agencies include the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR), Petroleum Products Pricing Regulatory Agency (PPPRA), Petroleum Equalization Fund (PEF), Petroleum Trust Development Fund (PTDF), the Nigerian Content Development Monitoring Board (NCDMB), Nigerian Nuclear Regulatory Agency (NNRA) and Petroleum Training Institute (PTI). They accused the OAGF of insisting on enrolling their members on the IPPIS platform without taking into consideration the peculiarities of the oil and gas industry with regards to the Collective Bargaining Agreement (CBA) and approved pay structure between the unions and the federal government through the Salaries, Wages and Income Commission. Besides, they said the OAGF's insistence on the enrolment of the affected agencies on IPPIS did not consider that they were already enrolled on the revived Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS).

2.3 Theoretical Explication

This study adopts the Frustration-Aggression theory as the theoretical framework to substantiate this work. Postulated by Dollard, Doob, Mowrer, Miller and Seare (1939) the frustration aggression theory argues that people are motivated to act aggressively by a drive conducted by frustration. In proposing their frustration aggression theory, Dollard *et al.*, (1939) suggested that aggression is always a consequence of frustration... the existence of frustration always lead to some form of aggression. Thus, the central thrust of the theory is that aggression is always the result of frustration and anger, especially when we feel thwarted in our attempt to get our ambitions and objectives fulfilled.

The concept of frustration denotes condition that arises when goal attainment is blocked, while aggression constitutes actions aimed at harming perceived stumbling blocks (Jegade and Ajayi, 2008). It is implied that frustration will inevitably lead to some form of aggression. When the aggrieved do not have easy access to the stumbling block, they take out their violent response on symbolic representation of the imagined enemy and express in an indirect way (Hewstone and Stroebe, 2001; Cited in Jegede and Ajayi, 2008).

2.4 Empirical Verification of IPPIS

Through the primary methods used in gathering data in this study, over 275 academic and non-academic staff of University of Uyo were observed, interviewed or served with structured questionnaire, respectively in the course of this research. The number cuts across various departments majorly in the Town Campus of the University like: Political Science/Public Administration, Sociology, Economics, Geography, Communication Arts, Chemistry, Physics, Mathematics/ Statistics, Medicine, Pharmacy, Education, Law, Agriculture, etc.

In one of such interviews with a Professor (name anonymous) in the Department of Chemistry, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria on the need to reflect his thoughts in this research, as an individual Lecturer in Uniuyo, and what he also thinks can serve as a representation of the general position of other Lecturers in his University, the Professor had this to say, *“I’m sure that there is no one that is embracing IPPIS as a payment platform”*.

In a similar vein, a Senior Civil Servant at the rank of Grade Level 12 in the Akwa Ibom State Civil Service (name also anonymous) who provided some useful materials for this work revealed that,

IPPIS isn't implemented in Akwa Ibom State and I doubt its implementation by states in Nigeria – I'm not that conversant with its operation. Akwa Ibom utilizes a fully automated payroll system through which serves the purpose.

While Olumuyiwa (2018) studied the effectiveness of integrated payroll and personnel information system in addressing ghost worker syndrome in Nigerian public sector, Folorunso and Simeon (2021) took time to carry out comprehensive empirical investigations on what various scholars have extensively written about Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) within its short time of implementation in Nigeria as referred to some of them below.

According to Olumuyiwa (2018), the paper employed the use of primary and secondary data to explain the opinions of public servants in the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), with a population (450) consists of senior and junior workers of administrative, finance and audit departments comprise the population of the study. The three departments were directly sampled in human resources and salary administration in three senatorial districts in Lagos State. The finding of the study revealed that the strategies adopted by IPPIS addresses ghost worker in the public sector in Nigeria. It further showed that the introduction of IPPIS policy into the salary administration in Nigeria improved constant payment of employees, with observance that there are still challenges facing IPPIS in uploading monthly salary of the employees.

Micah and Moses (2018) examined IPPIS and the Ghost Workers' Syndrome in Nigeria's Public Sector. Adopting the historical research method, the study concluded that the introduction and its implementation of integrated personnel and payroll information system (IPPIS) have to a reasonable length mitigated the incentive, capacity and opportunity of fraudulent individuals to perpetrate payroll fraud at all levels. Nonetheless, few challenges were observed as technological barriers and that Major MDAs are yet to connect to the IPPIS platform over a virtual private network. Thus, it is recommended that MDAs at all levels should key into the IPPIS platform in line with the Federal Government Public sector reform agenda to minimize payroll fraud in Nigeria. Enakirerhi and Temile (2017) studied the challenges, benefits and prospects of IPPIS in Nigeria. The study submitted the benefits of IPPIS to include; accurate and reliable personnel information, reduction or elimination of corrupt and

sharp practices, facilitation of modern scientific and accurate budgeting and forecasting, streamlining payroll and personnel, confidence in payroll cost, prompt deductions and remittance to all third party funds, (PAFs, NHIS, NHF, FIRS, State Boards of Inland Revenue). Saving of funds to government from the ghost worker syndrome, improvement in management reporting and information and observed few challenges to skills transfer problem, poor supporting infrastructure, technological barriers for infer MDAs transfer, resistance from stakeholders and lack of will for accelerated implementation. Thus, concluding that the future looks bright with the implementation of IPPIS which is set to serve as an avenue for budgeting projection and planning as well as database for national statistics and reduction in government cost.

Haruna, Joseph and Samson (2015) examined integrated personnel payroll and information system (IPPIS) panacea for ghost worker's syndrome in Nigerian public service. Adopting the survey design and sampling 393 out of 24,671 staff of Kogi state local government commission. Simple percentages, means score and Spearman rank order correlation coefficient. The study observed that ghost worker's syndrome is highly imminent in the public service thus; recommends that the integrated personnel payroll and information system (IPPIS) should be adopted in the public service to ensure a virile economy through enhance productivity.

Effiong, Oro, Ogar, Raphael, Etop and Iroushu (2017) examined treasury single account (TSA), integrated payroll and personnel information system (IPPIS), and integrated financial management information system (IFMIS): application and implementation effects on fraud management in the public sector in Nigeria. Underpinning the study using Meta Theory Model, Circumvention Innovation Theory and Public Finance management theory, the descriptive research design was employed, and questionnaire administered on respondents randomly selected from the studied Ministries and linear regression model was employed in establishing the relationship between variables, the study concludes TSA, IPPIS, and IFMIS have positive and significant relationship with Fraud and fraud management as well as jointly impact the performances of Public Interest Entities. Thus, recommends that IPPIS be fully implemented to address the ghost worker's syndrome in Public Interest Entities and that public officers be technologically trained to effectively utilize TSA, IPPIS and IFMIS platforms.

2.5 Value Impact on the Nigerian Economy

Value is measurable, and in this context, value is monetized. IPPIS has come to stay as a mechanism to curtail mismanagements, misrepresentations and abuse of office in the public sector. Prior to the introduction and implementation of IPPIS several challenges have loomed the public sector environment making accountability and transparency difficult to assess in public finances. To mention, ghost workers which in most cases is perpetrated by top government officials, tax avoidance and evasion as a result of inefficient tax computation in government offices salary over and under payment issues and lack of accountability in government spending. This case has cost the government money. The pilot test of IPPIS in February 2006 showed a positive shift in the ministry case studied. Going on live in April 2007, the 7 ministries involved showed that IPPIS will provide a paradigm shift in government accountability.

Effong *et al* (2017) observed that the benefit of TSA, IPPIS and IFMIS is positively significant as it has proved to be a mechanism through which fraud in the public sector can be curbed and drastically reduced. Furthermore, Ekakirerho and Temile (2017) outlined that IPPIS provides accurate and reliable personnel information, reduces and eliminates corrupt sharp practices in public offices as well as facilitate modern scientific and accurate government budgeting and forecasting. One of the menaces prior to the emergence of IPPIS and still resident in many MDAs and other government parastatal is the “Ghost worker”. This problem usually perpetrated by top government officials to accumulate and receive salaries and other benefits on non-existing employees has continually increased personnel cost beyond the actual. IPPIS has since inception uncovered this fraudulent activity in the enrolled MDAs. Recently, 78,315 ghost personnel were revealed in the Nigerian Police Force (NPF). Evidence from Rivers state universal basic education board in July, 2011 reported an annual loss of ₦2.4billion to 1477 ghost workers.

Same way, the National Identity Management Commission uncovered 4,000 ghost workers in December 2011. The Niger state government discovered in 25 local government areas, not fewer than 20,000 ghost workers, the list goes on unending of the several discoveries made in MDAs of ghost workers and excessive payment of salaries and other benefits. Post implementation of IPPIS, the Federal government in July, 2013 identified 46,821 ghost workers in 215 MDAs (Micah and Moses 2018). Olumuyiwa (2018) study shows that IPPIS policy into payment administration has improved constant payment of salaries. Published reports showed that from 2007 to 2019, IPPIS

implementation in MDAs, NPF and other paramilitary agencies has saved the government over ₦ 600 billion (Armed, 2019). The quality of government payroll administration has vastly improved and an increasing number of MDAs are moving away from manual payroll administration.

The MDAs have the necessary information for planning their personnel costs. IPPIS has actually reduced corruption by virtually eliminating ghost-worker syndrome where applied, thereby reducing the cost of governance. The Scheme has, from its launch in 2007 to December 2014, saved the government ₦185 billion (about US\$1 billion), representing the difference between the money that government would have released to MDAs based on their estimated nominal roll submissions and the amount actually paid through the IPPIS platform. A breakdown of this show that ₦416 million was saved in its first month of operation and ₦12 billion at the end of its three years' pilot phase. The scheme now covers 359 MDAs and has successfully enrolled 237,917 members of staff and weeded out 60,450 'ghost workers'. Furthermore, it reduced the red tape involved in manual payroll administration (BPSR, 2015).

Other very many tangible beneficial impacts of IPPIS are already evident and gave credence to the fact that these reforms are not only desirable but also expedient has been recorded. The impacts include: Improved governance as reports are now timely and reliable. This has added a higher level of transparency to public finance management. For instance, the statutory financial statement for year ended 31st December 2018 has been forwarded to the auditor general for the Federation in line with constitutional provisions. Improvement in the reduction of cost of governance hitherto spent on manual processes. The massive financial losses occasion by payroll fraud and ghost-workers' syndromes are gradually being eliminated by the introduction of IPPIS in MDAs. Savings have been made, which is been used to enhance overhead capital expenditure in MDAs. The introduction of IPPIS has now brought greater confidence in the accuracy and reliability of government financial information and this has boosted and help encourage foreign and private owners of resources to do business with the Nigerian government.

For Folorunso and Simeon (2021), scholars have extensively written about Integrate Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) within its short time of implementation in Nigeria. For instance, Farajimakin and Anichebe (2017) studied the effects of Integrated Personal Payroll Information System on Employees' Welfare: Evidence from Federal Ministries in Nigeria the study was based on survey and descriptive research design and the data were

collected using questionnaire structured in hinaty format. Binary logistic regression analysis was employed. The result of the study showed that, the implementation of IPPIS had weak positive relationship with employee welfare but it was statistically significant.

In another study by Farajimakin and Anichebe (2017) on Integrated Payroll System and Government Recurrent Expenditure in Nigeria. The study used both qualitative and quantitative method of research. Data were collected through primary and secondary sources. The secondary was collected from annual reports of Bayelsa State Government, Nigeria and survey data were obtained from 30 respondents using researcher-designed questionnaire validated by experts and shown to have a reliability coefficient of 0.90. Descriptive and ordinary least square regression statistical techniques were used in analyzing the data with the aid of Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. The study found that, there was positive and strong relationship between integrated payroll system and personnel cost and overhead cost.

In the study of Leyira and Temple (2018) on IPPIS and the Ghost Workers Syndrome in Nigeria's Public Sector. The study adopted a historical research method and its finding was that the implementation and deployment of Integrated Personnel and Payroll Management System (IPPIS) have to a great extent reduced the incentive, capacity and opportunity of fraudulent individuals to perpetrate payroll fraud at all levels.

While the study by Agboola (2018) on Effectiveness of Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System in Addressing Ghost Worker Syndrome in Nigerian Public Sector was a survey research. The study utilized primary and secondary sources of data to elicit the opinions of public servants in the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The study revealed that there were still challenges facing IPPIS in uploading monthly salary of the employees. The study concluded that with the introduction of the IPPIS scheme, if properly implemented and managed, it will go a long way in eradicating ghost workers in the Nigeria public service.

The study by Mela (2019) on the Implementation of IPPIS Policy in the Nigerian Universities by the Federal Government: Benefits and Challenges. The study was a qualitative research typed. The study revealed that, university system did not reject IPPIS but argued that IPPIS did not adequately capture university flexibility and peculiarities.

In their own study, Kaoje et al. (2020) which focused on Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) and Transparency in Government Payroll Administration in Nigerian Civil Service: A Unique Approach. The study was carried out with descriptive cross-sectional survey research design. The study found a significant moderate positive relationship between IPPIS, Transparency and Accountability.

Enakirerhi and Temmile study on IPPIS in Nigeria: Challenges, Benefits and Prospects. The study was a theoretical one that relied on various federal government announcement, opinions, stakeholders, presentations to international bodies and various articles and newspaper publications to reach its conclusion. The study found that accurate and reliable personnel, reduction or elimination of corrupt and sharp practices, facilitation of modern scientific and accurate budgeting and forecasting were major benefits of IPPIS. These benefits according to the study were however threatened by skills transfer problem, poor supporting infrastructure, technological barriers for inter MDAs transfer, resistance from stakeholders and lack of will for accelerated implementation.

Idris, Adaja and Audu (2015) study on Integrated Personnel Payroll and Information System (IPPIS) Panacea for Ghost Workers Syndrome in Nigerian Public Service. The study elicited data from both primary and secondary sources. The data were analyzed using the simple percentage, frequency tables, mean score and spearman rank order correlation technique. The study found that ghost-workers' syndrome was rampant in the public service and that the integrated personnel payroll and information system (IPPIS) if properly adopted in the public service, it would ensure a virile economy through enhance productivity.

Effiong et al. (2017) study which examined the Effects of Treasury Single Account (TSA), Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS), and Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS): Application and Implementation Effects on Fraud Management in the Public Sector in Nigeria. The study was conducted using descriptive research design with questionnaire administered on respondents randomly selected from the studied Ministries. The linear regression model was employed in establishing the relationship between variables and the study finding showed that TSA, IPPIS, and IFMIS have positive and significant relationship with Fraud and fraud management as well as jointly impact the performances of Public Interest Entities.

2.6 Justifications/Criticisms

The justifications or gains, from the government's point of view are the list of achievements agreed to have recorded over the short period that IPPIS has been piloted or test-run in the country, while on the other hand, the criticisms that trail the policy are mainly from those who have been affected by the process of implementation of IPPIS in the country, particularly, workers in the Federal Universities in Nigeria. In their eyes of criticisms, the supposed beneficiaries see such as challenges and 'pains' of IPPIS on workers in the country.

From the official records in the Office of Accountant General of the Federation, OAGF (2020) as cited in Folorunso, et al. (2021), below are the 'gains' and the 'pains' of IPPIS implementation in Nigeria:

The Gains of IPPIS are outlined as follows:

- i. Improved prompt and regular payment of salaries of MDAs;
- ii. Facilitation of prompt deductions and remittances to the accounts of all third-party stakeholders e.g., PFAs, NHIS etc.;
- iii. Over N361 Billion savings in personnel cost recorded between 2017 and 2019;
- iv. Financial/personnel variances trend is easily accessible and available;
- v. It makes personnel planning/budgeting easy since IPPIS is also a personnel management tool;
- vi. Enforcement of compliance with due process on employment;
- vii. IPPIS big data in various organizations are being transformed into a rich source of information which could be leveraged to make rich decision about government operations;
- viii. Many of the Departments and Agencies having realized that personnel cost was no longer coming to them for direct disbursement, embarked on recruitment to utilize their approved manpower/personnel budget; Between September, 2011 and 2020, so many Nigerians have been employed in the MDAs thereby reducing unemployment rate in the country; and,
- ix. MDAs are getting used to the application and many are currently managing their payroll at their respective offices without recourse to IPPIS Secretariat.

Others include:

- x. Elimination of unauthorized personnel workforce (ghost workers) from Government payroll;
- xi. Easy retrieval of personnel information of all public servants under the scheme;
- xii. Reduction in personnel records' falsification record of service (including age, length of service; etc.;

- xiii. Salary/monthly emoluments are paid to all public servants on the scheme same day no matter the location within the country without delay;
- xiv. Actual personnel cost paid monthly/annually are easily accessible with reason(s) for fluctuation easily given;
- xv. The scheme programmed automatic stoppage of payment to personnel due for retirement as a result of length of service, age and tenure thus reducing wastage or unauthorized payment;
- xvi. All third parties' payment (cooperative deduction, tax, NHF and Union dues, etc.) are affected from employee's salary and paid directly and promptly to beneficiaries account on behalf of payee with schedule of payment made available to the beneficiaries;
- xvii. Unapplied/unutilized fund are easily monitored;
- xviii. Planning/budgeting for training of personnel can now be done easily since IPPIS is also a personnel management tool;
- xix. Saving to government as a result of personnel cost over-budgeting.

The Pains of IPPIS include:

- i. Deliberate Institutional resistance by many MDAs in joining IPPIS in the face of set deadline for enrolment. Stiff resistance from the unions in the Tertiary Institutions more especially ASUU in the Universities and resort to incessant blackmail of IPPIS on the media for self-seeking objectives;
- ii. Inadequate Infrastructure: Poor internet connectivity to the Primary Data Centre (PDC) by MDAs on IPPIS and inadequate computer hardware for IPPIS Role Players. This inhibits efficiency and effectiveness in service delivery;
- iii. The IPPIS application has not been fully utilized. Of the seven modules on the software, only the payroll module is in appreciable use. The Human Resource modules, which are meant to manage staff recruitment, posting, promotion, training, discipline, and disengagement, are yet to be fully deployed for use by MDAs Service-Wide. The current vendor has not delivered everything contracted and paid for and the project management of the initiative has been weak;
- iv. Most of the IPPIS Staff in the MDAs have not been exposed to Oracle Training and some of the few that received the training have been deployed to other MDAs;
- v. Lack of Synergy between MDAs Desk Officers and OAGF: Finding revealed that lack of effective synergy between the two major partners

was a major setback for IPPIS implementation. The WhatsApp platform created for IPPIS Desk Officer by Office of the Accountant General of the Federation for the purpose of interacting about the challenges bedeviling the IPPIS implementation has not be active. It is ridiculous that members of the platform have never for once met to discuss about these challenges and there was no official meeting to interface with the officials of Office of the Accountant General of the Federation;

- vi. Delayed Response to complain and over-centralization: Public servant who is victims of under/over payment or complete omission of salary experienced a lot of difficulty in getting their cases addressed. Some who are working outside Abuja after series of unattended complaints from their MDAs Desk Officers resulted into travelling to OAGF in Abuja with more financial burden to shoulder. Often times, they were reversed to their MDAs Desk Officers from Abuja without solution while others get the problem fixed in Abuja. But the stress and timeline of getting the complaint addressed put such victims in more precarious condition because lots of unmet needs which might demotivate workers;
- vii. Lack of Technological Transfer: Most often, there are two-way technical hitches experience by the officials of the OAGF who claimed the consultants did not show them the complete technical know how to handle the platform properly while the MDAs Desk Officers on their own part alleged the OAGF of not giving them enough access to the platform as well as technical knowhow. The exact location of IPPIS server is shrouded in secrecy;
- viii. Sharp Practices by IPPIS Handlers: The IPPIS project has also had some scandals coming from it. Police inspectors and rank and file under the Akwa Ibom State Police Command and some personnel of the Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps have called on the authorities to investigate inconsistency in the payment of their salaries. They queried the operation of the IPPIS, saying they suspect fraud. The police officers involved have been suffering underpayment of their regular salary every month since 2018 when payment of police salaries and allowances was moved from Mechanized Salary Section (MSS) to the IPPIS (Nduka, 2019). In his own testimony, the former Chairman of Independent Corrupt Practices and other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), Ekpo Nta alleged that “by outsmarting the Federal Government Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System (IPPIS), some public servants

allegedly collected salaries from four different federal ministries. Some unidentified software developers have unhindered access to the database of IPPIS and usually set up new users and change live data, from time to time”;

- ix. IPPIS and Corruption: Issuing of payment slip without salary payment is another corrupt practice in IPPIS office. Once the payment slip is being issued out the money is gone and nothing can be done. Even after writing complaints letter Months after the letter was written, the affected workers were unable to get any response. It was also alleged that there are cabals in the finance section of the IPPIS that embezzle monies meant for workers in the federal civil service but issue pay slips to show salaries are paid (Sahara Reports July 27, 2019).

It is evident with these afore-mentioned challenges that IPPIS has created some other challenges while trying to solve others. In other words, it can be inferred that IPPIS implementation has resulted in creating some challenges that adversely affected public servants and government.

2.7 The Nexus between Public Financial Management and IPPIS

In a non-empirical sense, one can conclude that PFM has a serious connection with IPPIS because they both deal with finances, and public finances at that. But, in a more scientific and empirical terms, it is imperative to specifically unbundle the topic of this research and use the variables in PFM to compare with the cardinal objectives of IPPIS and arrive at the nexus (connection) between the two concepts.

For instance, it would be agreed that Public Financial Management involves the economic processes and activities of sourcing for funds and utilizing and managing them effectively and efficiently in order to achieve the desired economic goals and objectives. In nutshell, ‘sourcing for funds, utilizing and managing them effectively and efficiently’ is about being in charge or in control. Therefore, IPPIS encourages ‘saving to government as a result of personnel cost over-budgeting’ which had led to the realization of ‘over N361 Billion savings in personnel cost recorded between 2017 and 2019’. Being in control also helps in ‘planning/budgeting for training of personnel’ which ‘can now be done easily since IPPIS is also a personnel management tool’ and makes ‘unapplied/unutilized fund...easily monitored’. With the centripetal and osmotic picture between PFM and IPPIS above, the research will go a step further to analyze and test the relationship between the two variables using the

four (4) major PFM indices below. These include:

- i. Resource allocation in the economy principle;
- ii. Promotion of equity in income and wealth distribution in the economy;
- iii. Economic stabilization through price stability, exchange rate stability, interest rate stability; and,
- iv. Economic stabilization through price stability, exchange rate stability, interest rate stability.

First of all, based on the resource allocation in the economy principle, there is a nexus with IPPIS objective that is about remittances to third parties. ‘Facilitation of prompt deductions and remittances to the accounts of all third-party stakeholders e.g., PFAs, NHIS, etc.’ Secondly, the Promotion of equity in income and wealth distribution in the economy is in line with the ‘Improved prompt and regular payment of salaries of MDAs’ as one of the objectives of IPPIS is in line with the financial principle of income and wealth distribution in the economy. Once workers are paid, income so mobilized are distributed and wealth are circulated around the country. The third index of analysis is the Stimulation of growth and development in the economy to ensure high level employment, per capita income and standard of living which has a serious connection with the IPPIS objective that encourages employment in Departments and MDAs.

Thus, ‘many of the Departments and Agencies having realized that personnel cost was no longer coming to them for direct disbursement, embarked on recruitment to utilize their approved manpower/personnel budget; Between September, 2011 and 2020, so many Nigerians have been employed in the MDAs thereby reducing unemployment rate in the country’. But, fourthly however, the only PFM principle that does not seem to agree with IPPIS is the Economic stabilization through price stability, exchange rate stability, interest rate stability index. This may be so because IPPIS as a whole has no control of the economy vis-à-vis the market forces. IPPIS only receives and spend.

3. Methodology

In order to arrive at the nexus between public financial management and IPPIS, particularly as it relates to staff salaries in Federal Universities, with University of Uyo in specificity, the study adopted a qualitative research paradigm. This methodology helped the researcher to carry out the combination of explanatory, descriptive and contextual approaches in arriving at the conclusion of the research.

According to Babbie and Monton (2001), explanatory research is based on an

inductive approach towards arriving at a dense description of the phenomena under investigation. Descriptive research has to do with unfolding situations or events and implies that the representations of reality of participants should be clearly related. Finally, the Contextual approach is based on attempt to understand events, actions processes and practices in participants' context, instead of generalizing results.

4. Summary of Findings

The study was carried out to investigate the nexus between public financial management and IPPIS as regard academic staff salaries in the Federal Universities in Nigeria, with a particular focus on the University of Uyo, Uyo, NIigeria. With three subsidiary objectives and appropriate research questions, the research arrived at three findings using the following null hypotheses to carry out empirical tests. The null hypotheses include:

- i. The intention of government did not seem right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria;
- ii. The study may not ascertain if the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has served the purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria;
- iii. There is no cogent reason for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU).

At the end of the study, it was found that government intention was actually right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria, but the pains associated with it far outweigh the gains of IPPIS, as an attempt to frustrate staff welfare which is tantamount to bad governance. Secondly, the study actually ascertained that not only ASUU kicked against IPPIS due to the fact that Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has not served its purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria, talk less of those of the Federal Universities, with the case of University of Uyo, in particular. Finally, the study found that there were very many cogent reasons for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), otherwise, other outstanding government agencies would not have followed suit as evidently shown below.

“Apart from ASUU, NNPC subsidiaries too opposed the plan to enroll on IPPIS. The affected agencies include the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR), Petroleum Products Pricing Regulatory Agency (PPPRA), Petroleum Equalization Fund (PEF), Petroleum Trust Development Fund (PTDF), the Nigerian Content Development Monitoring Board (NCDMB), Nigerian

Nuclear Regulatory Agency (NNRA) and Petroleum Training Institute (PTI). They accused the OAGF of insisting on enrolling their members on the IPPIS platform without taking into consideration the peculiarities of the oil and gas industry with regards to the Collective Bargaining Agreement (CBA) and approved pay structure between the unions and the federal government through the Salaries, Wages and Income Commission. Besides, they said the OAGF's insistence on the enrolment of the affected agencies on IPPIS did not consider that they were already enrolled on the revived Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS)".

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

At the end of the study, it is safe to conclude that based on the findings made in this research through the testing of the following null hypotheses:

- i. The intention of government did not seem right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria;
- ii. The study may not ascertain if the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has served the purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria;
- iii. There is no cogent reason for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU).

The researcher concluded that first and foremost, government intention was actually right at the inception of the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) in Nigeria, although the pains associated with it far outweighed the gains of IPPIS. Secondly, not only ASUU kicked against IPPIS due to the fact that Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) has not served its purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria, talk less of those of the Federal Universities, with the case of University of Uyo, in particular but a number of other outstanding government agencies also follow suit. On the final conclusion, there were very many cogent reasons for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), otherwise, other outstanding government agencies would not have followed suit as evidently shown in the summary of findings above.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Federal Government should listen to the complains of ASUU and endeavour to reduce to the barest minimum, the pains associated with IPPIS, or otherwise should replace IPPIS with UTAS. This is in line with

Micah and Moses (2018) who admitted that few challenges were observed as technological barriers.

2. The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) should follow dialogue with government and continue with persuasion to present UTAS as the alternative platform for payroll management rather than out-rightly kicking against IPPIS due to the fact that it has not served the purpose in 696 MDAs that are on IPPIS Platform in Nigeria, talk less of those of the Federal Universities, with the case of University of Uyo, in particular. Micah and Moses (2018) also observed that Major MDAs are yet to connect to the IPPIS platform over a virtual private network.
3. The Federal government should adopt the reasons for the outright rejection of IPPIS by Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), as the University is a research ground, and would have experimented on IPPIS and found that it is not the most efficient payroll system for the country. Hence, other outstanding government agencies would not have followed suit as evidently stated earlier. Enakirerhi and Temile (2017) studied the challenges, benefits and prospects of IPPIS in Nigeria and encountered resistance from stakeholders and lack of will for accelerated implementation.

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